

Epidemiological Profiles of Rotavirus and Norovirus in Pediatric Acute Gastroenteritis

Niran Kadhim F. Al-Rubaey

Department of Microbiology, Hammurabi College of Medicine, University of Babylon, Babylon, Iraq

Abdulkadir Kareem Rhumaid

Department of Technical Medical Laboratories, Institute of Medical Technology Al-Mansour, Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq

Zeena Jamal Alkhazraji

Department of Optometric Techniques, Medical Technical Institute Al-Mansur, Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq

Shatha Ahmed Alshami

Department of Optometric Techniques, Medical Technical Institute Al-Mansur, Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract

Background: Acute gastroenteritis (AGE) is the common reason for morbidity in children across the globe. Historically, rotavirus was the main cause of this burden, but the epidemiological landscape has changed with vaccine introduction. Recently, norovirus and other pathogens may be on the rise.

Methods: A hospital-based, cross-sectional study was conducted from January 2024 to January 2025. Stool samples were collected from 980 children under five years of age who presented with acute gastroenteritis. Samples were screened for rotavirus and norovirus using the rapid chromatographic immunoassay test and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Demographic and clinical data were collected and analyzed to identify risk factors and compare disease severity using the Vesikari scoring system.

Results: Out of the 980 children, 220 (22.5%) tested positive for norovirus, 194 (19.8%) for rotavirus, and 40 (4.1%) had a co-infection. Norovirus was the most frequently detected single pathogen. The highest prevalence for both viruses was in the 12–23 month age group. Norovirus infections peaked in the autumn and winter months, whereas rotavirus cases were concentrated in the late winter and early spring. Clinically, rotavirus infections were associated with a significantly higher mean Vesikari score (14.8 vs. 12.5, $p < 0.01$), longer duration of diarrhea (5.8 days vs. 4.5 days, $p < 0.05$), and a higher rate of severe dehydration (56% vs. 32%, $p < 0.01$) compared to norovirus.

Conclusion: Norovirus had been the predominant cause of viral AGE in this pediatric cohort post-rotavirus vaccine era, but rotavirus continued to be associated with greater disease severity. Altogether, these results indicated that norovirus causes a large disease burden and support the continued development and eventual implementation of a norovirus vaccine.

Introduction

Acute gastroenteritis (AGE) remains a formidable global health challenge, representing one of the most common infectious diseases in children under five years of age [1]. It is a leading cause of morbidity,

malnutrition, and, in low-income settings, mortality [2]. The clinical presentation of AGE is characterized by diarrhea and/or vomiting, which can lead to significant dehydration, electrolyte imbalance, and hospitalization [3]. While bacteria and parasites contribute to the

More Information

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etiology of AGE, enteric viruses are recognized as the predominant cause, accounting for approximately 70% of episodes [4]. Among these, rotavirus and norovirus are the most significant pathogens. For decades, rotavirus, a double-stranded RNA virus of the Reoviridae family, was the undisputed leading cause of severe, dehydrating diarrhea in infants and young children globally [5]. The immense burden of rotavirus-associated hospitalizations and deaths prompted the development of live-attenuated oral vaccines, which were introduced into national immunization programs worldwide starting in 2006 [6]. The implementation of rotavirus vaccination has been a major public health success, leading to dramatic reductions in severe rotavirus-related disease and hospitalizations in countries with high vaccine coverage [7]. The incidence of rotavirus declined, and norovirus has emerged from its shadow to become the leading cause of AGE in both community and healthcare settings in many parts of the world [8]. Noroviruses are highly contagious, single-stranded RNA viruses belonging to the Caliciviridae family [9]. Unlike rotavirus, there is currently no licensed vaccine for norovirus, and infection does not confer long-lasting, broadly protective immunity, leading to lifelong susceptibility to reinfection [6,10]. The clinical manifestations of rotavirus and norovirus gastroenteritis can be similar, often involving vomiting, watery diarrhea, and fever, making etiological diagnosis based on symptoms alone unreliable [11]. However, understanding the relative contribution of each virus is crucial for several reasons. First, accurate burden-of-disease estimates are essential to guide public health priorities, including the development and strategic implementation of new vaccines. With several norovirus vaccine candidates in clinical trials, precise epidemiological data are needed to define target populations and evaluate potential vaccine impact [12]. Second, continued surveillance is necessary to monitor the effectiveness of rotavirus vaccines and to detect the emergence of vaccine-escape strains or shifts in genotype circulation [4]. Third, identifying the specific viral agent can inform clinical management and infection control measures within hospital and community settings [1]. Despite the recognized importance of these viruses, there is a continuous need for contemporary, region-specific epidemiological data. Prevalence rates and genotype distributions can vary significantly based on geographic location, socioeconomic conditions, season, and the maturity of rotavirus vaccination programs [13]. The objectives of this study were (1) to determine the current prevalence of rotavirus and norovirus, including co-infections; (2) to describe the demographic and seasonal distribution of these infections; and (3) to compare the clinical severity of rotavirus- and norovirus-associated AGE.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

A hospital-based, cross-sectional study was conducted at the various hospitals and some of the primary health centers at different governorates in Iraq. Data and specimens were collected prospectively from January 2024 to January 2025. The written informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants prior to enrollment.

Study Population

This was a study of children who were aged ≤ 1 –59 months and either admitted to the inpatient ward or treated in the emergency department (ED) due to acute gastroenteritis syndrome. AGE was characterized by three or more loose or watery stools and two or more vomiting episodes within a 24-hour period, with an illness duration of ≤ 7 days.

Inclusion criteria were (1) an age < 60 months, (2) meeting the clinical case definition for AGE, and (3) a guardian able to provide informed consent. The exclusion criteria were (1) chronic diarrhea defined as lasting more than 14 days, disease-causing diarrhea other than infectious (such as inflammatory bowel disease); (2) a major, concomitant illness such as pneumonia or urinary tract infection requiring hospitalization; and (3) severe immune suppression.

Sample Collection

Stool samples were collected from 980 children under five years of age who presented with acute gastroenteritis. Upon enrollment, the form captured demographic information (age, sex, residence), clinical symptoms (date of onset, frequency and duration of diarrhea and vomiting, presence of fever, abdominal pain), and treatment details.

The severity of gastroenteritis was systematically assessed using the 20-point Vesikari Clinical Severity Score, which evaluates the duration and frequency of diarrhea and vomiting, fever, dehydration severity, and treatment requirements. Dehydration was clinically classified as none, mild-to-moderate, or severe by the attending physician. A single bulk stool sample was collected from each participant in a sterile, leak-proof container within 48 hours of admission [11]. Samples were transported on ice to the hospital's microbiology laboratory, where they were aliquoted and stored at -80°C until analysis [14].

Laboratory Methods

Rotavirus and Norovirus Detection

Rapid immunochromatographic tests (ICTs) represent a critical diagnostic tool for the early detection of rotavirus and norovirus, the leading viral causes of AGE in children worldwide. All 980 stool samples were first tested for rotavirus antigen using the COMBO CARD TEST kit provided by CerTestBiotec, Spain, and for norovirus antigen using the test provided by the Biofocus Company, South Korea. The processes were

executed in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

All ICT-positive samples were screened for rotavirus group A antigen and norovirus GI/GII antigens using commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits (RIDASCREEN® Rotavirus and RIDASCREEN® Norovirus, R-Biopharm, Germany). These sandwich ELISA tests utilize monoclonal antibodies against the conserved rotavirus VP6 protein and specific norovirus capsid proteins [11].

Statistical Analysis

All data were entered into a database, and all computations were done in STATA (StataCorp LP, College Station, TX, USA), version 16.0 [15]. A summary of demographic and clinical parameters was done using descriptive statistics. The Chi-square (χ^2) test, or Fisher's exact test, was used when required for comparing categorical variables. Differences in continuous variables were assessed using the Student's t-test for normally distributed data or the Mann-Whitney U test for non-normally distributed data. A p-value < 0.05 was assumed as statistically significant. Clinical predictors associated with rotavirus versus norovirus infection were identified by multivariate logistic regression and reported as adjusted odds ratios (aOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Results

Patient Demographics and Enrollment

Over the 12-month study period, a total of 980 children meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled. The median age of the cohort was 18 months (Interquartile Range [IQR]: 10–29 months). The study population consisted of 568 (58.0%) males and 412 (42.0%) females, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.38:1. The majority of patients (72.4%) resided in urban areas. Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Cohort (n=980)

Characteristic	Category	Number (%)
Age Group (months)		
	≤1–11	343 (35.0)
	12–23	382 (39.0)
	24–35	157 (16.0)
	36–47	68 (6.9)
	48–59	30 (3.1)
Sex		
	Male	568 (58.0)
	Female	412 (42.0)
Residence		
	Urban	710 (72.4)
	Rural	270 (27.6)
Primary Symptoms at Presentation		
	Diarrhea	980 (100)
	Vomiting	853 (87.0)
	Fever (≥38°C)	696 (71.0)
	Abdominal Pain	412 (42.0)
Dehydration Status		
	None/Mild	431 (44.0)
	Moderate	392 (40.0)
	Severe	157 (16.0)

Prevalence of Rotavirus and Norovirus

Out of the 980 stool samples assessed, a total of at least one enteric virus was detected in 454/980 (46.3%) children. Norovirus was the most frequent pathogen, with 220 (22.5%) cases identified. Rotavirus was found in 194 (19.8%) cases. 40 (4.1%) children were co-infected with both rotavirus and norovirus. Therefore, norovirus was identified as a lone agent infection in 180 (18.4%) children, and rotavirus presented as a single pathogen infection in 154 (15.7%) children. Distribution of each viral infection in general is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Prevalence of Rotavirus, Norovirus, and Co-infections in Children with Acute Gastroenteritis

Distribution by Age, Sex, and Season

Both rotavirus and norovirus infections were most prevalent in children between 6 and 24 months of age. The peak incidence for norovirus was in the 12–23 month age group (35.5% of all norovirus cases), while for rotavirus, the peak was slightly younger, in the 6–17 month range, though the 12–23 month group also had

a high burden (32.0% of all rotavirus cases). Infections were significantly less common in infants under 6 months and in children over 36 months (Figure 2). There was no statistically significant difference in the detection rates of either virus between males and females.

Figure 2: Age Distribution of Rotavirus and Norovirus Infections

The figure displays the number of cases for each virus across different age groups, showing a clear peak for both viruses in the 12-23 month category.

The seasonal analysis of rotavirus and norovirus infections revealed distinct but overlapping patterns of circulation. Norovirus activity began to increase in late autumn, with cases rising markedly in November and reaching a sharp peak during December and January. This finding highlights the strong winter association of norovirus transmission. Conversely, rotavirus cases showed a delayed onset, with infections starting to rise in January, peaking during March and April, and then declining rapidly by early summer.

These results suggest that while both viruses play a major role in acute gastroenteritis among children, their seasonal peaks differ considerably. Norovirus predominates during the winter months (December–January), whereas rotavirus reaches its maximum incidence in late winter and spring (March–April). Such seasonal variation is consistent with global epidemiological observations and emphasizes the importance of timely preventive measures, including vaccination, public health awareness, and hospital preparedness during the peak seasons to reduce the burden of gastroenteritis cases. Figure3.

Figure 3: Seasonal Distribution of Rotavirus and Norovirus Infections (Jan 2024- Jan 2025)

Clinical Characteristics and Severity

A comparative analysis of clinical features was performed for patients with single-pathogen infections (Table 2). The comparative analysis of clinical

manifestations between rotavirus and norovirus infections revealed that rotavirus predominantly affected younger children and was associated with more severe disease outcomes. Children with rotavirus

infection exhibited a higher frequency of fever (83.1% vs. 75.0%) and higher mean maximum body temperature (38.9°C vs. 38.5°C) compared with those infected by norovirus. Although vomiting occurred at similar rates in both groups, its duration was slightly longer among norovirus cases (3.1 vs. 2.8 days), whereas diarrhea persisted significantly longer in rotavirus infections (5.8 vs. 4.5 days). The severity of illness, as measured by the Vesikari score, was markedly higher in rotavirus (14.8 ±2.1) compared to norovirus (12.5 ±2.5), reflecting the greater clinical burden of rotavirus gastroenteritis. Furthermore, severe dehydration was observed in more than half of

rotavirus cases (56.5%) compared with nearly one-third of norovirus cases (32.2%), while mild or no dehydration was more common in norovirus infections. Consistently, prolonged hospitalization exceeding three days was significantly higher among rotavirus-infected children (66.2%) compared with norovirus (42.2%). Collectively, these findings underscore the greater severity and healthcare burden associated with rotavirus infection, highlighting its role as the predominant cause of severe pediatric gastroenteritis requiring hospitalization, whereas norovirus generally presented with a milder but still clinically significant course.

Table 2: Comparison of Clinical Manifestations in Patients with Single Rotavirus or Norovirus Infection

Clinical Manifestation	Rotavirus (n=154)	Norovirus (n=180)	p-value
Median Age (months, IQR)	16 (9–25)	19 (12–28)	0.08
Fever ≥38°C (%)	128 (83.1)	135 (75.0)	0.07
Mean Max Temperature (°C, ±SD)	38.9 (±0.6)	38.5 (±0.7)	<0.01
Vomiting (%)	141 (91.6)	166 (92.2)	0.85
Mean Duration of Vomiting (days, ±SD)	2.8 (±1.3)	3.1 (±1.5)	0.11
Mean Duration of Diarrhea (days, ±SD)	5.8 (±1.8)	4.5 (±1.6)	<0.05
Mean Vesikari Score (±SD)	14.8 (±2.1)	12.5 (±2.5)	<0.01
Dehydration Status (%)			<0.01
None/Mild	25 (16.2)	68 (37.8)	
Moderate	42 (27.3)	54 (30.0)	
Severe	87 (56.5)	58 (32.2)	
Hospitalization >3 days (%)	102 (66.2)	76 (42.2)	<0.01

Discussion

This hospital-based cross-sectional study provides a contemporary snapshot of the epidemiology of viral gastroenteritis in young children in the era of routine rotavirus vaccination. The present study observed the age distribution, with a peak incidence for both viruses in children aged 6–23 months, which is typical for these infections. This outcome is probably attributable to a decline in maternal antibodies and an immune system encountering these pathogens for the first time. The age distribution (74% ≤23 months) is therefore consistent with global surveillance syntheses and pre-/early-vaccine era hospital cohorts as documented by Aliabadi et al. [16], who stated that rotavirus- and norovirus-associated disease is concentrated in infants and toddlers; multi-region analyses report the majority of rotavirus hospitalizations in the first two years of life, with the highest proportions in the first year in high-mortality settings.

Also, the current study showed that the most cases predominately urban residence (72.4%). is plausible and has been variably reported. Some Iraqi and regional reports have observed higher burdens in urban referrals, while others noted higher rotavirus positivity in rural settings—differences likely driven by access to care, referral patterns, and sanitation gradients. This heterogeneity suggests local service-use and exposure

dynamics may shape your residence distribution. This is agreement with the previously documented by study conducted in Iraq [17]. However, This is disagreement with the other study conducted in Iraq [18], who, noted higher positive rotavirus and norovirus in rural area. Clinically, the high vomiting (87%) and substantial fever (71%) match canonical viral gastroenteritis presentations. Norovirus often presents with abrupt vomiting (frequently ≥80–90% of cases), while rotavirus is more often associated with higher fever and dehydration—features mirrored in your cohort’s fever rate and the 56% moderate-to-severe dehydration burden. These results agree with the results of local study reported in Diyala Governorate by Diraa et al. [19].

On the other hand, The dehydration profile (40% moderate, 16% severe) is compatible with published pediatric AGE cohorts where clinically significant dehydration is common at presentation, and it underscores the importance of early oral rehydration therapy recommended by clinical guidelines [3]. Furthermore, in this cohort of 980 pediatric stool samples, at least one enteric virus was detected in 46.3% of children. Norovirus was identified in 22.5%, rotavirus in 19.8%, and norovirus-rotavirus co-infection in 4.1%. These data position norovirus as the leading pathogen in your setting, closely followed by rotavirus.

This result is consistent with another study [20], which stated that the overall viral positivity (46.3%) is consistent with multi-pathogen surveillance from 2022–2023 showing ~45–50% viral detection among children with acute gastroenteritis (AGE), though rates vary by season, testing panels, and care setting.

The norovirus prevalence (22.5%) is slightly above recent global pooled estimates in pediatric AGE. A 2024–2025 meta-analysis focused on the post-GII.4 Sydney 2012 era reported a global pooled norovirus prevalence around 19% (16.7–21.4%), and broader syntheses over the last two decades place norovirus at ~16–18% in AGE cases. The concordance is strong, and the current study point estimate plausibly reflects winter sampling windows, local outbreak dynamics, and the high sensitivity of molecular assays [21, 22].

Conversely, our rotavirus prevalence (19.8%) sits within—but toward the higher end of—the range reported in recent pediatric series from the broader region, where studies commonly observe rotavirus proportions between ~15% and ~25% depending on vaccine uptake and calendar period. For example, a 2025 pediatric series reported rotavirus as the single most prevalent virus at 15.6% with a marked winter peak, and long-running hospital surveillance from the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia has shown substantial temporal variability in rotavirus detection spanning the pre- and post-vaccine eras [23]. In addition, the figure is also comparable to a Pakistani tertiary-care study [24], which observed that rotavirus was 27.5% and norovirus was 22.9%, underscoring that rotavirus remains prominent in hospitalized or tertiary-care cohorts even where vaccine coverage exists but is incomplete. Differences across sites likely reflect vaccine introduction timing/coverage, genotypic shifts, and care-seeking patterns.

The detected norovirus-rotavirus co-infection rate of 4.1% aligns with the growing recognition of mixed viral infections in pediatric AGE. A 2025 multi-pathogen study [25] highlighted frequent co-detection among rotavirus, norovirus, astrovirus, and adenovirus in children, and a 2024–2025 hospital-based analysis similarly emphasized that rotavirus and norovirus together account for a large share of admissions and that co-infections are not rare when broad PCR panels are used. Your co-infection proportion, while modest, is epidemiologically plausible and clinically relevant because co-infected children can present with more severe dehydration and longer symptom duration in some series.

On the other hand, the seasonal analysis in the present study shows distinct but partially overlapping circulation patterns for norovirus and rotavirus. Norovirus activity rises in late autumn and peaks in December–January, while rotavirus increases later and peaks in March–April. This pattern indicates a winter-

dominant transmission window for norovirus and a late-winter/early-spring peak for rotavirus, with important implications for the timing of hospital preparedness, case detection, and preventive messaging. These findings align with large-scale surveillance and epidemiologic reviews [10], which stated that they consistently report winter-focused peaks for norovirus in temperate climates, often concentrated between October and March and associated with lower temperature and humidity conditions that favor transmission. Mattison et al. [26] studies emphasize that norovirus returns to strong winter seasonality after COVID-19 disruptions and that seasonal peaks can vary in magnitude year-to-year depending on population immunity and circulating genotypes.

The rotavirus seasonality in our data, which shows peak incidence in late winter and spring, is also compatible with contemporary surveillance. Although rotavirus seasonality was disrupted during the COVID-19 period, several recent reports document a re-emergence of the pre-pandemic pattern with late-winter spikes and region-specific timing (some settings observe autumn–winter peaks, others late winter–spring). Vaccine coverage and local climate (temperature, humidity, rainfall) are repeatedly identified as modifiers of rotavirus seasonality and intensity [27, 28].

Moreover, the present dataset (Table 2) shows that children with rotavirus presented at a slightly younger median age (16 vs. 19 months) but experienced more severe illness by several clinical indices: higher mean Vesikari score (14.8 ± 2.1 vs. 12.5 ± 2.5), greater proportion with severe dehydration (56.5% vs. 32.2%), and longer mean duration of diarrhea (5.8 vs. 4.5 days). These intra-study patterns support the classical profile of rotavirus causing more severe systemic disease and prolonged diarrheal episodes in young children, which aligns with population-level evidence that rotavirus more frequently results in severe dehydration and longer hospital stays than many other viral causes of pediatric acute gastroenteritis [29]. Furthermore, the results correspond with results conducted by Indrawan et al. [2], who stated that patients with rotavirus had higher Vesikari scores and were associated with significantly more severe clinical outcomes. This evidence confirms the continued virulence of circulating rotavirus strains and underscores the ongoing success and importance of the vaccination program in preventing what is often the most severe spectrum of diarrheal disease. In addition, the finding that rotavirus causes more severe disease than norovirus is consistent with the other previous studies carried out in Egypt by Ibrahim et al. [11], although a meta-analysis reported by Riera-Montes et al. [30] has suggested that when comparing hospitalized cases, the severity can be comparable. The higher severity of

rotavirus may be linked to its distinct pathogenic mechanism, which involves a more profound disruption of intestinal epithelial function and fluid absorption [1]. In the present study, the longer average hospitalization and higher proportion of prolonged admissions (>3 days) among rotavirus cases (66.2% vs. 42.2%) mirror surveillance and hospital-based studies showing rotavirus as a leading cause of hospital use and severe outcomes among under-5s worldwide, although the magnitude of this effect has been tempered in regions with high rotavirus vaccine coverage. These findings therefore plausibly reflect either low vaccine coverage or a population in which vaccine impact is incomplete. The results are concordant with a robust body of evidence [10, 31] that rotavirus often produces more severe dehydration, higher severity scores, and longer diarrheal illness than norovirus in young children, while also acknowledging genotype- and setting-dependent exceptions—particularly for some norovirus strains. For interpretation and public-health implications, report local rotavirus vaccine coverage and, if available, genotype data for both viruses; these contextual factors will clarify whether observed severity differences reflect pathogen virulence or population immunity.

Conclusion

This study confirms the shifting etiology of pediatric acute gastroenteritis, with norovirus now being the most frequently detected viral pathogen in our region. While rotavirus vaccination has successfully controlled the incidence of severe rotavirus disease, rotavirus itself remains a virulent pathogen when infection does occur. The substantial burden of norovirus-associated illness, which currently lacks a preventive vaccine, represents a major unmet public health need. These findings strongly advocate for the acceleration of norovirus vaccine development and demonstrate the vital need for sustained, high-quality epidemiological surveillance to monitor these dynamic and impactful childhood pathogens.

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